

ABOUT THE DEMOCRATIZATION OF SCHOOL PRACTICES AND KNOWLEDGE

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the theme surrounding the democratization of didactic-pedagogical practices and school knowledge, in which the action and attitude of the manager are extremely important for this purpose to be achieved. Its scientific relevance is presented through the discussion of the thoughts of authors who reveal how everyday school life is rich in elements that transform it into a field of symbolic exchanges and the destruction of such a condition, in the name of harmony, sociability and equality, make it a lifeless place and unable to generate any type of expectation. Its social relevance is shown through the possibilities of making people understand that human existence cannot determine intra-school life, which is nothing more than a scope of what awaits the student, once outside of it. This is a bibliographical research, based on the authors' experience with school administration and the relationship of social psychology applied to particular phenomena. Classroom and schoolyard situations are modulations that cannot be taken as the final and determining point for life; it is a scope, a sociological experiment, where everything must be taken as an expression of the psychology of the object. Many projects can be carried out in the school space, considering the interest in expanding the dynamism of pedagogical relationships, without this destroying the conflicting existence of relationships between humans. Much worse than trying to impose an agenda of equality and harmony among students is the emasculation of the clashes that must occur, so that the dispute leads to excellence and provides an increase in intellectuality. Taking on, therefore, an

emancipatory proposal of the political-pedagogical project, which involves building a pedagogical practice of inclusion, where different socially constructed knowledge and different cultural forms are valued and problematized, requires, among other elements, that educators and pedagogical team know the social reality in which they operate, understand its determinants, know the history of historically silenced cultures, their organizational spaces, their cultural and resistance practices, as well as the educational process they build in their struggles.

Keywords: School management; Existential conflicts; School space; Object psychology.

INTRODUCTION

Reflecting on the democratization of school practices and knowledge in the organization of pedagogical work, through an emancipatory political-pedagogical project, implies, firstly, entering the daily life of the school, to analyze the meaning of its pedagogical practices in the process of producing subjects and of building a society project. It involves analyzing school pedagogical work, with a careful look at the curriculum, especially in defining the knowledge used in school practice.

According to Garcia (2003), we need to enter the school, and learn to look at its daily pedagogical practice, where it receives or rejects children, young people and adults who belong to The a certain class, a certain socio-cultural group, who have a certain ethnic and racial origin.

In this sense, it is essential to be clear that the school, as a historical and cultural institution, through the way it is organized, how it distributes its times and spaces, through the knowledge and cultural practices that it legitimizes or silences, marks the subjects who participate in it. interact and reinforce or contest a social historical project.

In this sense, Giroux and McLaren (1995) state that schools are ideological and political terrains from which the dominant culture 'fabricates' its hegemonic 'certainties'; but also places where dominant and subordinate groups define and repress each other in an incessant battle and exchange, in response to socio-historical conditions 'propagated' in the institutional, textual *and* experiential practices that characterize school culture and the teacher/student experience within a given time, space and place.

In this regard, Louro (1996) makes an important contribution to thinking about school as a space for the production of subjects, who define and redefine themselves based on their positions of gender, ethnicity, class, as well as the way the school organizes its work. pedagogical in time and space. It is in the organization, segmentation and ranking of subjects and activities, content and rooms that minds and bodies are educated, that subjects adjusted to

the needs of society are produced. Furthermore, the school building itself, in terms of its location, its internal organization, its symbols, is impregnated with values, with symbolic contents of the hidden curriculum, affirming or hiding knowledge, pointing out 'examples', indicating destinations. All this is due to the fact that,

Passing through school benches leaves marks. It allows distinctions between subjects to be established or reinforced. There you acquire a whole way of being and being in the world. Those who were at school and, in some cases, in certain schools have a special way of speaking and arguing, of dressing or moving. Their gestures, their steps, their words and their ears were trained and tuned by and for a type of ritual that is distinct, different from others, from other instances or domains (LOURO, 1996, p. 125).

Therefore, it is in the totality of its organization, its contents, its relationships, that the school teaches a *sui generis* and, at the same time, plural way of being, of relating, of interpreting and being in the world. There is no way to think and describe a teaching formula, *a priori*, because the results are products of the application of thought and individual experience, in such a way that what translates as learning is a product resulting from the interaction between the intrinsic world (idealized) and the extrinsic (realized) experience, achieved through conflicts of all kinds and their interpretation, a fact that can only happen in a future very distant from the reality experienced by the student.

Classroom and schoolyard situations are modulations that cannot be taken as the final and determining point for life; it is a scope, a sociological experiment, where everything must be taken as an expression of the psychology of the object; why,

It is in common day-to-day life, in routine and apparently banal actions, that the school produces and reproduces subjects in their diversities and inequalities. It is also in these everyday spaces that subjects construct their responses, their resistances and adherences, making themselves (LOURO, 1996, p.128).

Interpreting the thought above, in the logic of knowledge taught and learned and in the social relations of school pedagogical work, the school affirms its identity and builds individuals and all their idiosyncrasies. In this sense, it gains importance due to the social, cultural, intellectual and political experience it provides to students and the systematized knowledge it socializes, in a symbolic way.

The excessive vanity left by the patristic heritage, in which the priest, the enlightened person, the one sent by God and his teachings are those who are shown to be directly responsible for the learning that ended up transforming education and its entire project into an end in itself. From this, what resulted was a type of intellectual formation in which theory overlapped

practice and the efforts undertaken to change this structure have proven to be insufficient and ineffective.

Practical learning actions allow for a greater interrelationship between students, providing a broad exchange of knowledge, knowledge and doubts, hypotheses and exposing the conflicts that mark living situations and coexistence in social environments. Failure to understand this type of attitude or the desire to deny it is what has led the school environment to promote a condition of boredom and aversion to school life.

Many projects can be carried out in the school space, considering the interest in expanding the dynamism of pedagogical relationships, without this destroying the conflicting existence of relationships between humans. Much worse than trying to impose an agenda of equality and harmony among students is the emasculation of the clashes that must occur, so that the dispute leads to excellence and provides an increase in intellectuality.

This is the role of teachers and the pedagogical team, in order to promote a relationship of symbolic exchanges, in which groups are formed and adapt to what they expect for each particular situation. Forms of coexistence must be kept free, including even the exclusions caused by groups and their respective rites of passage.

In this context, Arroyo (1987, p. 19) states:

School happens much more in the courtyards, in fights, at entrance and exit times, in the decision to study or skip class, in the organization of time and spaces, in the very organization of transmission processes, in the logic that passes through the science taught. , finally, in the social relations in which the school work process takes place.

In the process of construction, execution and evaluation of the political-pedagogical project, it is necessary to interrogate the social relations of school work and the knowledge present in educational practice. Therefore, it is important to analyze which knowledge is considered valid and is present, historically, in the school's pedagogical work to be systematized, re-elaborated and appropriated by students and which is absent and the reason for such selection and omission.

The knowledge covered in the school curriculum is historically linked and is a reference to a culture. The Curriculum is understood by Saviani (1992) as a selection of knowledge within culture; culture is not just a natural process of human production; rather, it represents a process, where different groups try to establish their hegemony over others. In this sense, in a class society, it is necessary to understand which social groups were historically included in school work and which were excluded and the reasons for such selection/exclusion. Furthermore, it is

necessary to understand how the knowledge and cultural practices of historically marginalized social groups are worked on. In this context, it is necessary to understand how power relations define the knowledge that should be taught and learned in school work and which should be ignored in the didactic agenda.

In this regard, Santomé (1995) states that educational institutions constitute one of the most important places for legitimizing the knowledge, procedures, skills and ideals of a society or, at least of the classes and social groups that have decisive portions of power. Therefore, the content and cultural practices considered relevant to these groups are generally included in school work. And the cultures or voices of minority and/or marginalized social groups that do not have important power structures are often silenced, if not stereotyped, stigmatized and deformed; all of this with the sole purpose of nullifying their possibilities of action.

Gimeno Sacristán (1995) highlights that school culture delimited by the explicit curriculum and the real curriculum that occurs in school practice, or by that reflected in teaching materials, is far from representing all aspects of the culture of society, where the school system is located. , as the curriculum selects elements, values some components more, hides certain aspects of the culture that surrounds the school. As soon as,

The selected contents rarely have the same meaning for each individual. The lack of attention to this lack of cultural representation in the school curriculum immediately impacts inequality of opportunities and the capacity of school culture to provide students with tools that allow them to better understand the world and the society that surrounds them. The dominant culture in classrooms is that which corresponds to the vision of certain social groups: popular culture, youth subcultures, women's contributions to society, forms of rural life and disadvantaged peoples (except as elements of exoticism) the problem of hunger, unemployment, mistreatment, racism and xenophobia, the consequences of consumerism and many other problematic themes that seem 'uncomfortable'. Consciously and unconsciously, it produces a first veil that affects the social conflicts that surround us daily (Id., p. 97).

The statement above leads us to reflect on how important it is the way in which schools treat knowledge and culture in their educational practice, since, according to Silva (1995), the transmission, understanding and unequal appreciation of knowledge and culture makes it difficult access to systematized knowledge reduces the autonomy, the potential for organization and struggle of groups that do not have their history told and valued, thus legitimizing cultures, knowledge, the history of the dominant culture, of the winners, and above all, hiding the existing relationships between different groups in terms of categories of gender, race and social classes, reinforcing and reproducing social and educational exclusion.

In this direction, the political-pedagogical project has a fundamental role, in order to guarantee political intentionality in pedagogical work. Through it, a space for reflection can be built to understand the ideology present in different discourses and pedagogical practices, as well as to understand the role of the teacher in the production and fight for voice, in which,

The discourse of everyday life also points to the need for radical educators to see schools as cultural and political spheres actively engaged in the production of voice and the struggle for voice. In many cases, schools do not allow students from subordinate groups to ascribe authenticity to their problems and lived experiences through their own individual and collective voices. The dominant school culture generally represents and legitimizes the privileged voices of white middle and upper classes (GIROUX; MCLAREN, 1995, p. 147).

When analyzing, historically, school pedagogical work, we can see the marks of hegemonic cultures in the curriculum throughout its organization, in its pedagogical relationships, in its content, where the school, in most cases, has valued the history of heroes, knowledge and culture of hegemonic groups, asserting their superiority. Furthermore, it has naturalized the roles socially attributed to women and men, black and white, poor and rich, which contributes to cultural domination. In this context, it has silenced, deformed and reproduced prejudiced, authoritarian and anti-democratic stereotypes. This stance towards historical reality has contributed to the lack of understanding of the reason for being of social facts, to passivity in the face of reality, weakening the possibilities of resistance, indignation, struggle and construction of a cultural counter-hegemony, because how can it be changed a story, seen as natural, by people of inferior culture?

Education, according to Freire (1996), is always a form of intervention in the world, to change it or to keep it as it is. In this sense, if the political-pedagogical project is built from an emancipatory perspective, the education developed by the school must contribute to recovering the lost, denied, silenced voice of women, black people, Indians, peasants, the excluded class, recovering their history, question the reason for their silence, the submission and oppression they experienced.

If you want an education that aims at transformation, it is necessary to question these relationships, not accept them as natural, as insurmountable, as if they had nothing to do with the society in which you are immersed. If students and the community itself do not have their history told, valued and their cultural practices understood, they have more difficulty understanding themselves in the world, valuing their knowledge, their culture and having references for social identification.

In this sense, Tomaz Tadeu da Silva (1995, pp. 200-201) analyzes the curriculum as “a form of representation, of production of social identities, as a result of power relations”. Gimeno Sacristán (1995) understands the curriculum as the sum of all types of learning and absences that students obtain in the schooling process. It is the real culture that arises from a series of processes, such as decisions about what is going to be done in teaching and what is actually done, the way in which the content and organization of the pedagogical space is linked with the outside world. , relationships between groups, materials used, evaluation practices.

In this way, the school, based on its curriculum assumed in the political-pedagogical project, constitutes a space for the discussion and deconstruction of the relationships established, throughout history, between different classes, races, between women and men. It can contribute to understanding the reasons for discrimination and social exclusion, how they were constructed in the expression of history and how they manifest themselves in different cultural practices and social spaces.

ASSUMPTIONS OF THE POLITICAL-PEDAGOGICAL PROJECT

Having explained the guiding principles for the construction and implementation of the Political-Pedagogical Project, certain assumptions need to be ensured, so that it can fulfill its role of defining and articulating the pedagogical and political processes, selected by the school. These assumptions are configured, above all: in the character of a process, of permanent construction/reconstruction and, therefore, its objectives and results must be gradual, mediate and flexible; in the need to be built and developed with the participation of the school community that knows its culture, its problems, its expectations, its needs; in the clear explanation of its goals and the objective conditions given for its implementation, both at the infrastructural level and with regard to so-called *human resources* ; in defining a team that coordinates its implementation and development, because, although the entire community has responsibility for the Project, there needs to be leadership, ensuring its execution. This team that you lead must go through a rotation, that is, everyone must be given the opportunity to participate; in the procedural and systemic assessment of the Project's development, taking into account the need to make adjustments, when necessary.

PEDAGOGICAL INTERACTION IN SCHOOL ACTIVITY

Educating for citizenship means educating people capable of living, communicating and dialoging in an interactive world, in this new reality in which individuals recognize the interdependence of individual processes and collective processes.

An education that enables a harmonious and enriching coexistence between individuals presupposes the recognition of diversity. Knowing that one is different and that each one has the right to be so, unique and singular, requires a deepening of respect for others and understanding of them. It requires working not only on external spaces, the learning environments where relationships take place; but, above all, the internal space of each member of the group, enabling self-knowledge and, as a consequence, recognition of the other. By becoming aware of your own feelings and emotions, capabilities and limitations, it becomes easier to understand and guide your behavior in relation to others. Working together to face problems, provide solutions, carry out innovative experiences at school, always promoting a satisfactory organizational climate, is the great challenge of democratic management. This means, then, that it is necessary to develop skills to face such challenges. Not only develop your own, but also encourage the development of your colleagues' skills and competencies.

The manager needs to be the great articulator of the school, striving to create adequate channels of communication and interaction. While teachers are more involved in the educational dynamics and employees in carrying out their support tasks, the manager must be attentive to all aspects that guarantee the achievement of the school's objectives, maintaining a good climate among all individuals who are part of the school. school and local community.

The interaction between these people, at school, does not just mean *being together*, exchanging ideas or sharing day-to-day tasks; it means facing difficulties and overcoming disagreements. A group of people becomes a team when it manages to create a collective work spirit, in which personal diversity does not constitute obstacles; rather, they are transformed into riches that unite and complement each other in the pursuit of common goals.

It is necessary to work on diversity of points of view or behaviors as an enrichment factor for the group and as a way of expanding the particular vision of each individual at school, because at work, people live and interact with each other, communicate they arouse sympathy or antipathy, they come closer or further apart, they enter into conflict, they compete, they cooperate, they become friends, they are sincere or covert in their relationships. These factors

can be part of everyday life, in the development of your work, both bringing together and - separating people who express themselves in different ways. Education, family and school experiences, character and personality influence the way an individual interacts with others.

Individuals' reactions constitute [*and result from*] a complex process of human interaction, which is expressed in the form of verbal or non-verbal behaviors. It is necessary to understand each person's way of living, how they think, feel, behave, their values, their worldview. Do not forget these aspects when proposing collective work situations. Seek to understand why individuals act or react in a certain way ; respect each person's way of being and moment, without losing sight of the objectives that need to be achieved by the school.

Decisions are made by individuals and implemented by them. This means that the school's success must be fundamentally and irreplaceably supported by the competence, capacity for innovation and positive performance of the team's workforce. The activity that this will develop must always be thought-provoking and provocative to motivate and value everyone's contribution and, at the same time, accessible and safe, to convey confidence and prediction of success.

As a manager, you must always be attentive to the communicative process developed at school. Dialogue only exists when the parties are on the same plane. There is no dialogue when one party has a weapon, physical or symbolic, pointed at the other's head. The speech of someone who commands from the throne and wants the other to accept their arguments is not dialogue. Dialogue presupposes equality, an intersubjective relationship, and not the imposition of personal will, based on the position or function held. In school management, communication is one of the most relevant and complex aspects, given that the school community is made up of people with different personalities; therefore, with different perception capabilities, which can offer barriers to communication, causing people to understand the same message or idea differently.

Therefore, each team has its own dynamics, a peculiar operating structure. She has movement. Throughout the various phases of the team's life, participants can assume different roles. In this composition of roles, qualities are multiplied and difficulties are diluted. However, for the team to move forward, it is advisable for the manager to be the coordinator of the process and the encourager of collective work.

In its initial phase, a team requires a more directive coordinator: one who provides more information, one who organizes time, space, routine, tasks ; that clearly states what is intended; that facilitates the inclusion of people in the team. When it is more organized, the coordinator becomes less directive: suggests, discusses, gives opinions, values each person's participation.

Your challenge is to allow the exercise of confrontation, create a climate of trust and respect for differences, always paying attention to ensure that the team does not stray away from its greater objective.

If the team already shows signs of maturity, the coordinator only intervenes at specific moments, expanding discussions, providing theoretical support, promoting evaluation and new joint planning of actions. It must be noted, as a manager, the phase in which school teams find themselves and act according to their needs. If, in the initial phase, it acts in a more directive way, providing more information, organizing time, space, tasks, etc. If, in the more organized phase, suggest, discuss, value each person's participation, create an atmosphere of trust, always paying attention so that the team does not deviate from the objectives. If the team is in the mature phase, the need for intervention will be minimal. However, at any stage, intensify the dialogue, deal with the conflict in a balanced way, that is, follow what you proposed: intensely experience each stage or phase of the process, respecting each person's moment without losing sight of the reasons for everyone's participation. at school.

The presence of a leader is essential in the life of a team, and coordinating it requires procedures that allow creating a climate of democratic participation that overcomes authoritarianism, individualism, centralization of power, etc. Therefore, the manager must show a democratic stance, being open, innovative, flexible, demonstrating his desire to learn and receive help from the people he works with. He must know the values of the team whose coordination is entrusted to him, encouraging self-esteem, giving him the conditions to develop his duties, introducing changes, slowly, in accordance with the understanding and recognition of individual and collective needs.

It is important that the manager listens more and talks less and is always ready to listen to everyone. When making decisions, they must be open, shared, make clear the standard of work expected of each and everyone, and that *everyone* can participate. Management must be exercised naturally, valuing people, controlling words and observations, even those made in a joking tone that could hurt others.

Therefore, it is important that the manager seeks to develop in himself some aspects that favor interpersonal relationships at school. Some of them are indicated for your analysis:

- Entrepreneur - to achieve results.
- Flexible - to change behaviors and views.
- Dynamic - to assimilate and apply new techniques and new approaches.
- Creative - to develop alternative decisions and/or problem solutions.

- Updated - to keep up with advances in society.
- Adaptable - to face new situations.
- Decided - to face challenges and risks.
- Technical - to promote action, the “how to do it”.
- In addition to these aspects, some principles should guide the manager's work for the development of people who live at school:
- Interaction - union of ideas and actions, seeking mutual respect.
- Democracy - the process of participation, continuous learning of critical capacity and autonomy. Everyone has the same opportunity to participate and be citizens.
- Responsible freedom - exercising the right to develop one's own rules of coexistence as a team. There must be freedom to think and be, to be and do, and understanding of the meaning of the other's freedom.
- Cooperation - practiced on a daily basis, an exercise in growth for collective and individual development, in a participatory action that aims to achieve, in a shared way, satisfactory results for the team and not just personal achievements.

CONCLUSION

To better understand democratic management in public schools, it is important to consider the democratic principle, autonomy and identity of the school.

Therefore, the need to guarantee management with committed professionals is analyzed, as democratic management constitutes an important space where the entire school, whether political or pedagogical, is defined by the entire school community.

In this sense, the process of reflection on the practice adopted by the school collective, and the practices of each of its segments, is inseparable. However, one of the greatest challenges facing the school in the construction and management of the political-pedagogical project is to (re)build the relationship between the school and the community, based on the principle of democratic participation.

Democratic participation is understood as one in which the community that has a direct relationship with the school: the families of the students, or that has an indirect relationship: the other residents of the neighborhood surrounding the school understands the school as a public space and identifies themselves with this space, either because he fought for this school to exist, or because he recognized the importance of this institution in the formation of new generations, therefore, he needs to participate in the school's political-pedagogical destinies and practices.

In this way, the school can contribute so that the community can overcome the knowledge of experience made by a more critical knowledge, to participate in some way, in the production of knowledge that does not yet exist and in the school's destiny, with the true autonomy of the school. It will take effect when the collective becomes aware of the different points of view and arguments regarding ideas and decisions, thus contributing to the formation of citizenship.

Taking on, therefore, an emancipatory proposal of the political-pedagogical project, which involves building a pedagogical practice of inclusion, where different socially constructed knowledge and different cultural forms are valued and problematized, requires, among other elements, that educators and pedagogical team know the social reality in which they operate, understand its determinants, know the history of historically silenced cultures, their organizational spaces, their cultural and resistance practices, as well as the educational process that is built in their struggles.

From an emancipatory perspective, the school, in addition to being a social experience, a space for the reconstruction of knowledge, must constitute a sphere of critical reflection on the political implications of this knowledge and experience, the construction of a serious democracy, which implies changing the structures of society, reorienting the politics of production and development, reinventing power, providing justice to the dispossessed, also requires the development of tastes democratic work in the political-pedagogical work of the school, which is not done with disembodied words, but with reflection and practice.

From this perspective, education, for Freire (1997), necessarily involves the democratic intervention of the educator, the construction of a dialogical relationship and respect for the student, for their knowledge, which demands knowledge of the concrete conditions in which they live, which condition your thinking, your culture, your history. Knowing the reality in which students live is fundamental to have access to the way they think and understand what they know and how they know it.

The democratization of school practices and knowledge, which implies a political-pedagogical commitment, involves both the inclusion of different socially constructed knowledge and cultural forms, and the construction of a participatory pedagogical process, built with the students and not for the students, based on of a dialogical relationship, of exchange, of mutual teaching and learning, so that educators and students are subjects of the educational process.

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